

1 **The range of Xist transcriptional targets in non-small cell lung cancer: ROBO1.**

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6 We discovered aberrant activation of Xist in cancer, the non-coding RNA that silences duplicate X
7 chromosomes in females to execute dosage compensation, by studying whole transcription in
8 p53-sufficient and p53-deficient cancer cells (1). We next described high levels of Xist expression that
9 could be triggered by mutation or loss of either of two major tumor suppressors, p53 or Rb (1, 2). We
10 demonstrated a function for Xist in activation and repression of solid tumor gene expression, in humans
11 with breast cancer, driven by p53 loss, and demonstrated a role for the expression of these Xist-modulated
12 genes in subtype selection (instruction of tumor lineage) in breast cancer (3, 4). We also described the
13 existence of Xist ribonucleic protein (Xist RNP) complexes that putatively functioned to dynamically control
14 gene expression in transformed cells (5).

15 We describe here Xist control of transcriptional targets in the lung during transformation (6-9). We
16 demonstrate control of *ROBO1* gene expression by Xist and a role for this gene expression control in
17 subtype selection in non-small cell lung cancer. Xist activation is likely a widespread and relatively
18 common biological phenomena during solid tumor development and disease progression driven by loss of
19 tumor suppressor (p53/Rb) function. Xist influences subtype selection in non-small cell lung cancer by
20 modulating expression of a wide range of transcriptional targets.
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Results

Here we used cells engineered to contain an Xist transgene, Xist-positive (Xist+) human embryonic stem cell clones, and epithelial cells of the lung that exhibit Xist activation following genetic depletion of p53 (6-8) to demonstrate Xist functions in control of gene expression across the transcriptome and in tumor lineage specification (subtype selection) in lung cancer (9).

Figure 1: Expression of ROBO1 defines the squamous subtype in non-small cell lung cancer.

GSE74706

n=10 adenocarcinoma

n=8 squamous cell carcinoma

Probe ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	% DE
A_23_P80503	2.98E-02	-2.3499796	-3.90529	-1.02	ROBO1	4038/34183	88.2

In patients with non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), expression of endothelial cell adhesion molecule *ROBO1* defined the subtype (Figure 1). We discovered subtype-biased expression of *ROBO1* by measuring and comparing total transcription between adeno and squamous subtypes of the most prevalent solid tumor type affecting humans, NSCLC.

Figure 2: In Xist+ human embryonic stem cell clones, the ROBO1 gene is differentially expressed.

GSE87231

n=2 Xist- human embryonic stem cell (hES) clones

n=2 Xist+ hES clones

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
6091	7.44E-06	0.174	-4.4807535	-0.78043177	1167.33	ROBO1	469/17710	97.4

Xist expression in human embryonic stem cells was associated with differential expression of *ROBO1* at the clonal level when studying ES cell gene expression transcriptome-wide (Figure 2). In mice, Xist expression is activated following zygote genome activation, while in humans the start of Xist expression is observed between embryonic 4- and 8-cell stage and continues into pre-implantation development in the morula and blastula (10).

Figure 3: Transgenic insertion of a gene encoding Xist in human cells results in modulation of ROBO1 gene expression.

GSE68109

n=1 HT1080 fibrosarcoma cell line; vector control (5 day DOX induction)

n=2 HT1080 fibrosarcoma cell line with 1p Xist integration (5 day DOX induction)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
6091	5.37E-01	0.61	-6.17E-01	-0.3764999	660.25	ROBO1	3990/18311	78.2

1 In human cells engineered to contain an Xist transgene, forced Xist expression resulted in
2 significant activation of ROBO1 (Figure 3).

3 **Discussion**

4 We provided evidence here describing control of expression of the ROBO1 gene by the non-coding
5 RNA Xist and a role for Xist-driven gene expression control in lineage determination at the clonal level
6 during solid tumorigenesis in humans with non-small cell lung cancer. Like in humans with breast cancer,
7 Xist activation that occurs very early is important for subtype selection and imparts a lasting influence on
8 tumor gene expression at clinical presentation. We are currently studying the molecular mechanisms
9 governing transcriptional induction of Xist; repair of the DNA during replication and damage are candidate
10 pathways that regulate Xist activation (11-13).

Methods

We used datasets GSE68109, GSE87231, GSE272045 and GSE74706 and for this quantitative differential gene expression study of Xist expression in the primary tumors of humans with non-small cell lung cancer, of the adeno and squamous types.

References

1. Mamoor, S., 2023. The tumor suppressor p53 regulates Xist expression in certain cellular contexts.
2. Mamoor, S., 2024. The non-coding RNA Xist is activated by loss or mutation of the retinoblastoma tumor suppressor.
3. Mamoor, S., 2024. Xist is differentially expressed in human breast cancer and its expression is controlled by estrogen.
4. Mamoor, S., 2023. Xist induction following p53 disability is accompanied by Tet activation.
5. Mamoor, S., 2024. Identification of cell- and tumor-type-specific Xist RNA/protein complexes: KHDRBS1.
6. Kelsey, A.D., Yang, C., Leung, D., Minks, J., Dixon-McDougall, T., Baldry, S.E., Bogutz, A.B., Lefebvre, L. and Brown, C.J., 2015. Impact of flanking chromosomal sequences on localization and silencing by the human non-coding RNA XIST. *Genome biology*, 16, pp.1-16.
7. Sahakyan, A., Kim, R., Chronis, C., Sabri, S., Bonora, G., Theunissen, T.W., Kuoy, E., Langerman, J., Clark, A.T., Jaenisch, R. and Plath, K., 2017. Human naive pluripotent stem cells model X chromosome dampening and X inactivation. *Cell stem cell*, 20(1), pp.87-101.
8. Sunaga, N., Shames, D.S., Girard, L., Peyton, M., Larsen, J.E., Imai, H., Soh, J., Sato, M., Yanagitani, N., Kaira, K. and Xie, Y., 2011. Knockdown of oncogenic KRAS in non-small cell lung cancers suppresses tumor growth and sensitizes tumor cells to targeted therapy. *Molecular cancer therapeutics*, 10(2), pp.336-346.
9. Marwitz, S., Depner, S., Dvornikov, D., Merkle, R., Szczygiel, M., Müller-Decker, K., Lucarelli, P., Wäsch, M., Mairbäurl, H., Rabe, K.F. and Kugler, C., 2016. Downregulation of the TGF β pseudoreceptor BAMBI in non-small cell lung cancer enhances TGF β signaling and invasion. *Cancer research*, 76(13), pp.3785-3801.
10. Vallot, C., Patrat, C., Collier, A.J., Huret, C., Casanova, M., Ali, T.M.L., Tosolini, M., Frydman, N., Heard, E., Rugg-Gunn, P.J. and Rougeulle, C., 2017. XACT noncoding RNA competes with XIST in the control of X chromosome activity during human early development. *Cell stem cell*, 20(1), pp.102-111.
11. Mamoor, S., 2024. Control of Xist by BRCA1.
12. Mamoor, S., 2024. Control of Xist by Rif1.
13. Mamoor, S., 2024. Control of Xist by MRE11 indicates Xist activation in tumorigenesis is associated with double-strand break DNA repair.